

METHOD OF CREATING A STUDENT PORTFOLIO IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM AND POSSIBILITIES OF PRACTICAL APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

The article describes the role of the student's portfolio in the educational process of higher education, its content, and procedures for its use. The purpose, capabilities, main functions and content of creating a student's educational and professional portfolio are based on it. In the student portfolio, the tasks of the student, teacher and deputy dean have been determined, and the procedure for protecting the portfolio at the end of the academic year has been developed.

Key words: *innovation, pedagogical technology, portfolio, content, function, student, teacher, communicative, intellectual.*

INTRODUCTION

The use of innovative pedagogical technologies and modern technical means of teaching in the educational institutions of our republic has a significant impact on the quality of personnel. The development of innovative pedagogical technologies directly depends on the development of information technologies, the level of their ability to be used by teachers and students. Therefore, the development of pedagogical technologies affects the quality of personnel training, and the quality of personnel affects the improvement of production technologies. Therefore, it is necessary that pedagogical and production technologies are inextricably linked with each other,

improved based on the development of information technologies, and the information space is enriched with educational and production information [1].

Currently, many innovative pedagogical technologies are used in the educational process of the educational institutions of our Republic, they are being improved in accordance with the purpose and content of education. However, in accordance with the needs of the times, the innovative pedagogical technologies used in the educational process should be focused on the formation of reflexive competence in the student, that is, the student should complete the educational institution with confidence in the general cultural, general professional and professional qualifications acquired during the educational process, and first of all, he should be satisfied with this [2]. Therefore, we believe that the practical implementation of the "Student portfolio" technology aimed at the above goal and direction in all parts of the continuous education system of our Republic plays an important role in improving the quality of education.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Pedagogical observation, comparative analysis, generalization, pedagogical experiment-test, mathematical-statistical analysis, mental cards, expert survey of foresight, development of scenarios, future box, and Delphi methods were used in the research process.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Modern trends in pedagogical evaluation require the use of new technologies and systems of evaluation. Such an evaluation system requires full consideration of the student's level of mastery of communicative and intellectual skills, growth of competence, activity in studies and knowledge acquisition, as well as the exact dynamic change of training as a future staff [3]. The evaluation system used in the higher education system of our republic is a technology based on the point system, which takes into account the student's learning during the academic year. Of course, there are many positive aspects of the test system. But this system takes into account

only the student's educational activity, that is, the mastery level of subjects. In this system, only the science teacher evaluates the student's knowledge of science. Also, the student's activity in other fields, creative works, activity in public works are not taken into account. In other words, a student studies for a grade and tries to achieve it. Factors encouraging the development of reflexive ability in a student are rare. When a student who has graduated from a higher education institution goes to work, first of all he needs to believe in his knowledge and abilities as a specialist. For this, self-assessment, that is, an objective assessment of knowledge and skills, abilities, and opportunities should be formed [4]. One of the pedagogical technologies that create such opportunities is the "Student Portfolio". The portfolio is a personal creation of the student and he personally creates it in an electronic version. A folder of the student's achievements during his studies is attached to the portfolio. At the end of the portfolio period (at the end of the semester, course or study period), the student will present the materials in his portfolio.

The portfolio allows you to [5]:

- plans and properly organizes the personal trajectory of each student's competence formation during the entire period of study at the educational institution;
- provides a systematic and regular assessment of the student's self-knowledge and abilities, opportunities and shortcomings during the formation of professional competence;
- creates conditions for regular monitoring and objective assessment of the graduate's readiness for professional activity.

The portfolio complements the traditional control form and takes into account the student's activities in all areas (educational, creative, social, communicative, scientific, etc.). A portfolio can be created for a semester, an academic year, or the entire period of study at an educational institution.

The goal of creating a student's educational and professional portfolio:

- record the student's personal educational results and achievements in terms of quantity and quality;

- proper planning and objective assessment of the dynamics of professional competence formation of the student.

Functions of the student educational and professional portfolio [6].

1. It allows the teacher to plan, regularly monitor and evaluate the formation of student competence within his subject.

2. Assessment of the student's educational and scientific achievements. On the basis of mastering the educational courses, the portfolio is filled with the achievements of the student on the way to achieving competence, necessary for a successful professional and academic career.

3. Assessment of preparation for professional career. The portfolio contains evidence of the student's professional growth throughout the course of study.

Content of student activity [7]:

- the student's own activity on the formation of competence plans;
- communicates independently to get advice from the teacher in order to complete the portfolio;

- he analyzes the results of his activities in order to achieve the goal set in the formation of competence;

- creates a portfolio independently, chooses the materials in it himself.

- at the end of each academic year, the portfolio to the dean's office submits;

- prepares a short report confirming his readiness for professional activity;

- presents a complete portfolio at the end of production practice;

- conducts a presentation of portfolio materials.

The content of the teacher's activity [8]:

- the teacher implementing the educational program provides help and advice in planning the organization of his activity on the formation of competence in the student in the field of his subject;

- develops practical tasks aimed at the formation of professional competence;

- advises the student and coordinates his activities during the entire study period;

- evaluates the results of the student's activity and gives a conclusion about the level of the student's development of relevant competence during the reporting period;
- participates in portfolio presentation, informs students about various types and levels of competitions.

Activities of the Deputy Dean for Academic Affairs:

- is responsible for the implementation of the portfolio in the educational process;
- develops regulatory documents in this direction and summarizes the results of activities;
- informs the Scientific Council of the faculty about the results of the implementation of this technology;
- organizes training-methodical seminars and consultations on the problems and difficulties that arise in the implementation of the portfolio.

Portfolio composition:

A student portfolio includes [9]:

1. Information about the owner of the portfolio (FiSh, place and year of birth, actual address of residence, name of OO'Yu and field of education). This section also includes information about the student's life and professional goals and interests.
2. Content of the student's educational, educational-methodical, scientific and extracurricular activities aimed at forming general cultural, general professional and professional competence.

At the beginning of each academic year, a competence formation plan is drawn up within the scope of the student's educational, methodological, scientific and extracurricular activities, taking into account the subjects taught in the student's educational program and educational and professional practices.

At the end of the academic year, the achievements achieved in the goal of competence formation are analyzed and evaluated by the student himself.

3. Conclusion justifying the student's readiness for professional activity will be done.

The complete material of the student's portfolio and the conclusion on readiness for professional activity are presented by the student with the participation of teachers, students, parents and external experts.

CONCLUSION

It is the application of the portfolio technology that allows the full manifestation of the student's inner potential, self-activation, and self-assessment. In this technology, the student's knowledge does not completely depend on the teacher, he becomes more independent and adequately evaluates and proves his knowledge, that is, the student studies for self-development, improvement, activation and assessment. The student's teaching-methodical portfolio is an innovative pedagogical technology aimed at monitoring, evaluating, developing the student's activities in various fields and creating reflection based on the student's self-evaluation.

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